

Next-Generation Optical Transceiver and Switching Solutions Exploiting MB and SDM

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Abstract—Novel multiband (MB) and spatial division multiplexing (SDM) transceiver and node architectures, capable to exploit spectral (wavelength-band) and spatial dimensions, are presented as suitable options to target potential capacity scaling of future optical networks. A proof of concept assessment of the proposed transceiver is performed demonstrating MB (C+S)+SDM transmission after 19-cores MCF of 25.4 km.

Index Terms—Multiband transmission, spatial division multiplexing, optical networks, sliceable transceivers.

I. INTRODUCTION

Global mobile network data traffic is forecast to grow by a factor of 3 by 2028 [1]. Hence, future 6G networks and systems should be able to efficiently handle the increasing traffic growth and number of users and devices without sacrificing performance, requiring a paradigm shift towards enhancing capacity/bandwidth and reducing cost and energy consumption. The joint exploitation of cutting-edge technology such as multiband (MB) and spatial division multiplexing (SDM) will give suitable tools to meet next generation 6G requirements, advancing network capabilities to overcome the coming “capacity crunch” of conventional optical fiber systems. By the adoption of bundle of standard single mode fibers (SSMFs) or specialty fibers such as multicore fibers (MCF) or multimode fibers (MMFs), SDM can be exploited transmitting different signals through multiple spectral channels [2]. Additionally, MB technology enables the use of spectral bands beyond C-band, such as L-, S-, O-, E- or U-band, enhancing the overall available bandwidth [3]. MB+SDM transmission will present some challenges that should be considered in the design of future optical systems and networks. Specifically, the most appropriate technology option for the different network building elements (i.e. fiber types, amplifiers, multiplexers (mux) and de-multiplexers (demux) and switches) should be selected in order to exploit the available bands and spatial channels taking into account the related transmission impairments. On this regard, new transceiver and switching solutions with advanced capabilities should be investigated in order to meet the required network capacity scaling. In this paper, a MB+SDM sliceable bit rate/bandwidth variable transceiver (S-BVT) and a MB+SDM optical node architecture are envisioned as potential flexible and high-capacity solutions to meet future capacity needs and traffic increase. A proof of concept of the proposed transceiver is assessed achieving 73 Gb/s MB+SDM transmission after 19-cores MCF of 25.4 km. The proposed transceiver and switching solutions could be adopted in different segments of the network according to the

enabled capabilities and considered technologies. A partially exploitation of the proposed solutions could be envisioned, for example for the metro/aggregation network segment in a medium-term ($\approx 5-9$ years) scenario, only enabling a specific set of bands (i.e. C+S+L-bands).

II. MB+SDM S-BVT ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 1. MB+SDM S-BVT architecture and proof of concept.

A MB+SDM S-BVT approach is presented as a solution to exploit network flexibility and scalability towards meeting 6G requirements. The MB+SDM S-BVT is composed of multiple building blocks, namely the bandwidth/bitrate variable transceivers (BVTs), that can be enabled/disabled following a pay-as-you grow approach according to the changing network demands. Thanks to the exploitation of multiple dimensions including (space, bands and wavelength) the proposed transceiver can target suitable capacity scaling by considering multiple slices working at different bands (i.e. S+C+L-bands) and wavelengths that can also be transmitted through different spatial channels (fiber cores/modes of MCFs/MMFs or bundles of SSMF). The transceiver architecture based on external modulation and direct detection (DD) is depicted in Fig. 1. At each bandwidth/bitrate variable transmitter (BVTx) side, adaptive orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM)

digital signal processing (DSP) is performed to create a digital signal, which is analog converted by means of a digital to analog converter (DAC). The DSP block includes parallelization, adaptive mapping (according to bit and power loading, BPL, algorithm implementation), training symbol (TS) insertion, inverse fast Fourier transform (IFFT) implementation, cyclic prefix (CP) insertion, serialization and radio frequency (RF) upconversion operations. Then, the electrical OFDM signal is optically modulated with a tuneable laser source (TLS), which can work within different bands, and a Mach-Zehnder modulator (MZM). The different slices are aggregated/distributed with a MB optical aggregator/distributor, which can be based on different approaches, such as programmable wavelength selective switches (WSSes), passive optical band pass filters (BPFs) or a combination of both. This allows including the possibility to perform single sideband (SSB) modulation and increase the transmission robustness against fiber impairments [4]. At each bandwidth/bitrate variable receiver (BVRx), the different slices are amplified and filtered by considering the most suitable technology for the amplification and filtering stages according to the operation band [4]. Finally, the filtered signal is photodetected with a simple PIN photodiode followed by a transimpedance amplifier (TIA) and analog-to-digital converted (ADC) to perform the receiver adaptive DSP. The DSP block at the receiver includes RF downconversion, parallelization, CP removal, FFT implementation, equalization and TS removal, demapping and serialization.

III. TECHNOLOGY OPTIONS FOR MB+SDN NODES

In view of the high-capacity/bandwidth and flexibility targets of future optical networks to support over 10 Pb/s by the end of this decade, a new breed of optical switching technologies should be exploited with advanced capabilities [2]. Current wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) SSMF-based networks includes reconfigurable optical add-drop multiplexers (ROADMs), which employ WSSes in a route-and-select topology, and/or optical cross connects (OXC) offering wavelength switching granularity. Different technologies can be considered to enhance node capabilities towards supporting additional granularities, including spectral (wavelength-band) and spatial degrees of freedom, in an efficient manner [2]. A MB+SDM scalable node based on a multigranular architecture of three layers (WDM, MB and SDM layers) is envisioned to enable spectral and spatial switching, as seen in Fig. 1 and table I. Specifically, the WDM layer consists of a N -degree ROADM that can include multiple $1 \times N$ -ports WSSes to provide wavelength switching granularity. The MB layer can be based on a band OXC with band demux/mux or other currently investigated novel switching devices, such as band selective switches (BSS) [2]. The SDM layer exploits the spatial dimension by considering spatial switching over MCFs. The spatial switch can consist of multiple $1 \times K$ ports fan-in (out) SDM demux/mux with an OXC matrix (which can be implemented with a photonic space switch based on polymer optical waveguide [5]) or recently proposed solutions based on core selective switches (CSSes) [6].

Fig. 2. Numerical evaluation of (left) XT per wavelength and (right) XT vs MCF length considering C+S+L-bands transmission.

IV. NUMERICAL ANALYSIS ON MB+SDM TRANSMISSION

Several transmission effects can occur when adopting MB+SDM technology, that can lead to signal degradation and loss, limiting the overall system's performance. Specifically, nonlinear effects such as Raman scattering can appear, in MB transmission, causing a power transfer between wavelengths with 100 nm spacing. This depends on several factors, such as fiber length, frequency separation between the channels and signal power [7]. On the other hand, when implementing SDM, the crosstalk (XT) effect impacts on the transmission performance, leading to a periodic power transfer between neighboring spatial channels. In particular, in MCF transmission, the XT can be estimated by considering a simple analytical expression [8], as detailed below:

$$XT_{\mu} \approx \frac{2k_{pq}^2 R_b}{\beta \Lambda} L, \quad (1)$$

where R_b is the bending radius, k_{pq} is the mode linear coupling coefficient between two neighboring cores, L is the fiber length, Λ is the core pitch and β is the propagation constant [9]. According to equation 1, numerical analysis of the impact of XT in different transmission bands is performed considering a 19-core MCF of 25.4 km. Specifically, we assume $R_b = 7.95$ cm, $\Lambda = 34$ μ m and a core radius of 3.94 μ m. The estimated XT versus wavelength (considering S+C+L bands), is depicted in the inset of Fig. 2 (left). From the figure, it can be seen that L-band is more affected by XT, whereas in S-band it is below -27 dB.

Additionally, the XT is also evaluated considering different spans of MCF up to 279.4 km and three different wavelength within S+C+L-bands, as depicted in Fig. 2 (right). Specifically, 1500 nm (S-band), 1550.12 nm (C-band), and 1600 nm (L-band) are investigated. According to the results, the XT increases at the increase of the MCF length, being L-band the most affected one. Specifically, at 279.4 km a 12 dB XT difference is appreciated between L- and S-bands. The S-band arises as a potential spectral band to be exploited in MB+SDM systems due to the limited presence of the XT in MCF.

V. EXPERIMENTAL ASSESSMENT

A preliminary proof of concept of the MB+SDM S-BVT, presented in Fig. 1, has been here assessed enabling two OFDM slices of 20 GHz bandwidth (at C- and S-bands). The TLSes are set to 1550.12 nm (C-band) and 1500 nm (S-band), as, according to section IV, these bands are the most robust to the XT. A DAC working at 64 GSa/s and an oscilloscope,

TABLE I
PROPOSED TECHNOLOGY OPTIONS FOR ADVANCING OPTICAL SWITCHING GRANULARITIES

Granularity	Enabler technology	Capabilities	Scalability
Wavelength	ROADM with $1 \times N$ WSSes	High flexibility (Each WDM channel provisioned and routed with adaptive bandwidth; flex-grid granularity).	Scalable to high number ROADMs port counts
Band	i) Band OXC with $1 \times M$ Band demux/mux; ii) Multiple BSS	i) Cheap and simple technology. Band granularity; ii) Compact and rapidly reconfigurable but low mature technology. Route-and-select topology at the band level	Both architectures scalable to support large number of MB channels
Space	i) Spatial OXC and $1 \times K$ Fan-in (out) SDM demux/mux; ii) Free space-optics based on multiple $1 \times K$ CSS	i) Mature and very low loss technology. Coarse granularity; ii) High cost-efficiency and low insertion loss but low mature technology	Both architectures scalable to support a large number of MCFs

Fig. 3. Experimental SNR profile considering the transmission over the MCF.

OSC (as ADC) working at 100 GSa/s are used. Regarding, the DSP, 512 OFDM subcarriers and 4% and 1.9% overheads due to TS and CP are respectively considered. Different modulation formats are implemented, including BPSK and m-QAM ($m = 2^l$; $2 \leq l \leq 8$), according to the BPL algorithm for adaptive mapping. Two BPFs are included to emulate the MB optical aggregator/distributor element. Additionally, a WSS is considered, for the C-band slice, to perform SSB modulation. At the preamplification receiver side, an erbium doped fiber amplifier (EDFA) and a semiconductor optical amplifier (SOA) are considered for amplification of the C- and S-band contributions, respectively. A 19-cores MCF of 25.4 km is included in the setup for the experimental assessment. A target BER of 4.62×10^{-3} , considering a hard decision forward error correction (HD-FEC) threshold of 7% overhead, is fixed and ensured in all the achieved results. The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) profile of the MB+SDM transmission after the 25.4 km of MCF is depicted in the inset of Fig. 3. It can be seen that the C-band slice is more robust to the CD due to the implementation of the SSB modulation. The S-band slice has limited performance, since it is double sideband and thus more affected by the CD. Specifically, for the C-band, 51.4 Gb/s capacity is ensured at 4.3×10^{-3} after transmission through the MCF. Thanks to the implementation of the BPL algorithm, the S-band slice can also be transmitted through a neighbouring MCF core, achieving 21.4 Gb/s at 4.6×10^{-3} BER. The S-band performance is also limited due to the SOA high noise figure. Specifically, SDM transmission over the 19-

cores MCF of 25.4 km introduces 10 dB of attenuation, which should be compensated at the MB+SDM S-BVT receiver side. Thanks to the modular transceiver approach, additional slices, within the available wavelengths/bands, can be enabled and transmitted towards multiple spectral channels towards meeting future capacity needs of optical networks.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

New disruptive network approaches should be investigated to provide higher bandwidth, spectral and energy efficiency and capacity to support the growing demand and the emergence of new applications and services with stringent requirements, expected within the incoming 6G era. Hence, exploiting spectral (wavelength and band) and spatial degrees of freedom, with the adoption of advanced MB+SDM transceiver and node architectures, will enable to meet the needs of future optical networks. A proof of concept of a modular MB+SDM S-BVT has been assessed demonstrating MB (C+S) transmission after 19-cores MCF of 25.4 km. It has also been found that the L-band slice is more affected by the XT, according to the achieved numerical results. Additional transceiver slices within the available wavelengths/bands can be enabled considering further spectral channels towards providing the required capacity/bandwidth targets of next-generation optical networks.

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